

Teaching English Online Through the Use of Instagram in the New Normal Era of Covid-19

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ABSTRACT

Everyone has an Instagram account in this digital age. Lecturers use Instagram as a medium for developing English language teaching. This study presented teaching English online through the use of Instagram in the New Normal era of Covid-19. The data were analyzed using quantitative and qualitative research standards. The first data of this quantitative study was taken from the Survey through a questionnaire. Survey is a procedure in quantitative research that involves the use of a questionnaire to explore population characteristics, attitudes, behaviors, and opinions. Then, the researcher used qualitative research to serve the results of the interview data. There are three results of the study. First, that English Speaking is the dominant in teaching English online. Second, Grammatical English as the difficult English skill. Third, There are benefits of Instagram.

1. Introduction

Recently, people prefer to spend their time with their gadgets. They are very close to social media. Social media is generally defined as a type of electronic communication as a website for social networking and microblogging through which users create online communities to share information, ideas, private messages, and other content such as videos (Merriam-Webster Dictionary, n.d) and technology integrites, interactions social media, and content creation to jointly link online information (types of social media, 2013, paragraph 1). Kaplan and Haenlein (2010) created a classification scheme consisting of six types of social media: collaborative projects (e.g., Wikipedia), blogs (e.g., Twitter), content communities (e.g., YouTube), social networking sites (e.g., Facebook), world virtual games (eg, World of Warcraft), and virtual social worlds (eg, Second Life). Davis III, Deil AMEN, Rios-Aguilar, and Gonzalez Canche (2012) defined social media technology (SMT) as web-based and mobile applications that enable individuals and organizations to create, engage, and share ideas or content in various forms of communication. in a digital environment.

In the new normal era of covid-19, learning and teaching is still done online. So that lecturers try as much as possible to use interesting teaching media in order to achieve learning outcomes. One of the media used is the popular media Instagram. So it is necessary to

analyze the results of using Instagram's popular media in teaching English. This study focuses on Analysis in Teaching English Online through the Use of Instagram in the New Normal Era of Covid-19. This study is entitled " Teaching English Online through the Use of Instagram in the New Normal Era of Covid-19. Researchers conducted an analysis on student accounts. What was analyzed was the student captions posted on their Instagram accounts with the hashtag #learningenglishwithmrsade

2. Literature Review

Instagram media is very popular in the era of gadgets like today. Social media is the online communities in which people interact to each other. Social networking activities have the possibility of enhancing lecturers' professional and adding media/ways in their teaching. The lecturers will be close with their students and will be interactive to enrich English students competences. The students and the lecturers can organize activities such as writing skill, grammar understanding, and etc, Agustriana. (2017). Instagram is a photo- sharing mobile application that allows users to take pictures, apply filters to them, and share the on the platform itself. Instagram has over 400 million active monthly users who shared over 40 billion pictures, Alhabash, S., and Ma, M. (2017). According to previous research that social media is an online community where people interact with each other. Social networking activities have the possibility to improve the professionalism of lecturers and add media / means in their teaching. The lecturers will be close to their students and will be interactive to enrich the competence of English students. Social media is a digital and online community for building interaction with others.

3. Research Methodology

The participants were students from the Nahdlatul Ulama University of Purwokerto. They are in the second semester of the 2020/2021 academic year. The researchers provided a statement questionnaire to find out their responses/perceptions) of teaching English online through the use of Instagram in the new normal era of Covid-19. Interviews were also taken from students as participants. This data was analyzed using quantitative and qualitative research standards. The first data of this quantitative study was taken from a survey through a questionnaire. Questionnaires were delivered to each of the 11 students. Each student completed and returned a questionnaire. The questions in the questionnaire were set to obtain information about their perceptions. The results of surveys conducted among participants are calculated as a percentage. There are some results from participants' responses about the perception of using Instagram in English subjects at the Nahdlatul Ulama University of Purwokerto.

4. Findings

This study aims to find out in depth about Teaching English Online through the Use of Instagram in the New Normal Era of Covid-19.

Table 1. Students' responses to the questionnaire items

Questions	Q 1	Q 2	Q3	Q4
The questions about	Influence	Dominant English skill	Difficult English Skill	Benefit
Total students	11	8	8	11
Percentage	100%	72.7 %	72.7 %	100 %

Knowing the dominant English skills in teaching English online via Instagram. Knowing skills that are difficult to develop in teaching English online through the use of Instagram in the new normal era of covid-19. Knowing about benefits of Instagram.

From the data analysis process, we can see the findings:

1. English Speaking is the dominant English Skill
2. Grammatical English as the Difficult English Skill
3. Benefits of Instagram:
 - Creative Writing
 - Improved Vocabulary Insights
 - Expression Media and Confidence Building

5. Discussion

5.1. English Speaking is the dominant English Skill

English is a Second Language Acquisition, in this context the application of English requires habituation and an environment that supports the process of mastering English. Speaking is an ability that must be continuously trained. Armed with practice and the courage to speak one can improve the quality and ability in speaking English. To have good speaking skills, of course, you must be trained with various media. An effective medium is audio-visual, in this context is the creation of content on Instagram. Participants said that with Instagram they would be trained in their speaking skills.

Picture 1. Instagram content

Picture 2. Instagram content

Picture 3. Instagram content

Picture 4. Instagram content

5.2. Grammatical English as the Difficult English Skill

According to Alufohai (2016).P. grammar at the sentence level is fundamental for writing compositions in English. There are many rules in grammar, including articles, parts of speech, sentence patterns, and tenses, etc. (Cook and Ricard, 1980) quoted in Muhsin (2016, p. 81). The results of the research analyzed by the researcher showed that 72.7% of the sample students said that the English skill that was considered difficult was grammar, because students had to make sure of the tenses of the caption substance or the uploaded Speaking video. really double check because the content is Go Public.

5.3. Benefits of Instagram

5.3.1. Creative Writing

A finding showed that all participants felt some benefits from using Instagram in their English Teaching. Through Instagram, students can write their English assignments and express their creative writings. It stimulates students to write creatively. Based on interview data that students feel happy and short to explore their English skills in writing. This can stimulate their competence to find vocabulary to get good sentences in their texts. Students are required to post and create hashtags for their lecturers on #learningenglishwithmrsade.

5.3.2. Improved Vocabulary Insights

The participants get an increase in vocabulary. When they start writing Instagram captions, they prepare well about sentence diction or when creating content in the form of videos. Students prepare text or narratives that will become content on Instagram, so that students' vocabulary knowledge increases.

5.3.3. Expression Media and Confidence Building

Students feel that Instagram is a medium of expression to convey ideas and content. In addition, creating Instagram content can build confidence in speaking practice or in writing captions. After that, students can upload the content. And can give each other likes the content or leave comments. Through Instagram, students can share ideas and express their English skills. Because they are directly involved in the process of making videos or writing captions on Instagram. This will increase students' self-confidence because they are trained to appear in Instagram content and everyone can see and comment on the students' Instagram captions/content.

6. Conclusion

The conclusion of this study are; (1) English Speaking is the dominant English skill (2) Grammatical English as the difficult English Skill (3) Benefits of Instagram: Creative Writing, Vocabulary Insight Improvement, Expression Media and Confidence Building. Suggestions from this study are for further researchers to maximize video content to improve English Skills.

References

- Agustrianita. (2017). Teachers' Perceptions Towards Social Media Use to Improve Professional Development and Integration in English Language Teaching. *English Language and Literature International Conference (ELLiC)*. (1).17-22.
- Alhabash, S., and Ma, M. (2017). A Tale of Four Platforms: Motivations and Uses of Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, and Snapchat Among College Students?. *SAGE Journals*, pp. 1-3.
- Babbie, E. and Baxter, L. (2004). *The Basic of Communication Research*. California: Wadsworth Thomson.
- Cresswell, J., W. (2010). *Research Design: Pendekatan Kualitatif, Kuantitatif, dan Mixed*. Edisi Ketiga. Yogyakarta: Pustaka Pelajar.
- Cresswell, J., W. (1998). *Qualitative Inquiry and Research Design: Choosing Among Five Traditions*. California: Sage.
- Denzin, N.K. and Lincoln Y.S. (1994). *Handbook of Qualitative Research*. Thousand Oaks, London, New Delhi: Sage.
- Gadamer, H.G. (1976). *Philosophical Hermeneutics*. Berkeley: University of California Press.
- Geertz, Clifford. (1973). *The Interpretation of Cultures: Selected Essays*. New York: Basic Books, Inc., Publisher.
- Gracyk, Theodore. (2001). *I Wanna Be Me: Rock Music and the Politics of Identity*. Philadelphia: Temple University Press.
- Girik Allo, M.D. (2020). Is the online learning good in the midst of Covid-19 Pandemic? The case of EFL learners. *Jurnal Sinestesia*, 10 (1). Retrieved from <https://sinestesia.pustaka.my.id/journal/article/view/24>.
- Hamm, Charles. (1983). *Music in the New World*. Anthology of American Music, Inc. USA.
- Hammel, William M. (1972). *The Popular Arts In America*. 2nd ed. Harcourt Brace Jovanovich, Inc. USA.
- Hall, S. (1981). Encoding/Decoding in S. Hall, D. Hobson, A. Lowe and P. Wills (eds) *Culture, Media, Language*. London: Hutchinson.
- Iser, W. (1987). *The Act of Reading: A Theory of Aesthetic Responses*. London and New York: Routledge & Kegan Paul.
- Jauss, Hans Robert. (1974). *Aesthetic Experience and Literary Hermeneutics*. Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press.
- Lindlof, T.R. and Taylor, B.C. (2002). *Qualitative Communication Research Methods (second ed)*. Sage Publications, Thousand Oaks, CA.
- Lowenfeld, V. & Brittain, W.L. (1982). *Creative and Mental Growth*. New York: Macmillan Publishing Co. In
- Mamattah, R., Selorm (2016). *Students' perception of e-learning*. (Master Program Adult Learning and Global Change), Linköping University, Linköping.
- Parakriti T. Simbolon, (2007), *menjadi Indonesia*, Jakarta : Kompas. Sardar, Ziauddin and Van Loon, Borin. (1997). *Cultural Studies for Beginners*. Cambridge: Icon Books Ltd.